

NCSBN

Leading Regulatory Excellence

Optimizing Online Calibrations:

Strategies for Polytomous Item Sets in Computer
Adaptive Tests

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Research Design

50-Item CAT

Item Results

Item Results

Item Results

Maximum RMSE

Item Results

Standard Deviation RMSE

Item Results

Mean SEM

Item Set Results

Item Set Results

Item Set Results

Maximum RMSE

Item Set Results

Standard Deviation RMSE

Item Set Results

Mean SEM

